

Action Research for Professional Growth in EAL Practice

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Abstract: *Professional Learning is a core component of the ongoing work of teachers. Professional learning focussing on English as an additional language or dialect (EAL/D) is particularly needed for teachers in schools that have high numbers of students with EAL/D. Very few teachers learn about EAL/D in their initial teacher education degrees, but by the nature of the linguistic diversity of their classes, many teachers have found themselves to be teachers of EAL/D and in need of EAL/D-specific content and pedagogical knowledge and teaching strategies. Professional learning that includes classroom action research, where teachers can directly put into practice what they learn and engage in cycles of trialling their new learning in their own classroom context and responding to it, is particularly impactful on both teachers' own learning and on the use of the new learning with students. This article describes one context of professional learning with action research for EAL/D and then shares four examples of practice. It is anticipated that this model of teacher professional learning, together with the examples of innovative and effective EAL/D strategies, is worthwhile sharing with other teachers of EAL/D.*

Keywords: EAL/ EAL/D/ ESL/ EFL, English as an additional language, English as a second language, action research, professional learning, classroom approaches/strategies

Introduction

Many classrooms across the world have students with a diversity of languages. In Melbourne Australia, the context of this article, 33% of students are learning English as an additional language or dialect (EAL/D) (Victorian State Government Department of Education and Training, 2020). This poses a unique challenge for teachers in that they are not only teaching the curriculum content of their classes, but also English, which is the medium of instruction. For the EAL/D learners, they need to make progress in all aspects of their learning, through English, whilst they are learning

English (Department of Education and Training Victoria, 2019). Supporting EAL/D learners in their primary school years of learning can span many years. Research shows that newly arrived EAL/D students can take two years to develop English for social interaction, at least five years to develop the language to engage with age-appropriate curriculum, and students with disrupted or limited prior schooling can take an average of seven to ten years (Cummins, 1996; Cummins, 2008 in Department of Education and Training Victoria, 2022). Therefore, teachers need to cater for the unique learning needs of EAL/D learners throughout the primary school years (and for many years from arrival for new arrivals at later time points at school).

Teachers need to regularly participate in professional learning for ongoing teacher growth and development. In the context of Australia, it is a key requirement to participate in professional learning to meet annual teacher registration requirements. Most schools have very high numbers of students with EAL/D so all teachers are teachers of EAL/D, even though very few of them have had EAL/D training in their initial teacher education degrees. For this reason, professional learning about EAL/D is very popular. Action research linked with professional learning provides a unique opportunity for teachers to directly explore what they have learned, in their own classrooms with their students, straight away, to trial new strategies and find out what works and doesn't work in their contexts and with their learners. It also provides a collaborative environment for teachers to share their learnings and experiences with each other. It is within such a context of professional learning for growth in EAL/D teaching practice that this article reports on.

Literature Review

This literature review provides an overview of some of the key EAL/D teaching and learning theories and concepts that were shared and discussed in a series of professional learning in one school. Together with the theories and literature, an emphasis was placed on modelling classroom practices and sharing practical strategies and resources that teachers could use. These were then considered alongside teachers' existing practices, and teachers were encouraged to trial further strategies and/or make adjustments to their approaches in the form of action research, informed by this base of theories and literature.

Two foundational and related theories underpinning EAL/D teaching and learning are social learning (Vygotsky, 1978) and collaborative learning (Hmelo-Silver et al., 2013; Laal & Laal, 2012). These are based on a belief that learning, and language in particular, is a social experience (Vygotsky, 1978). This can be enhanced in the classroom by allowing students to have lots of talk time, work in collaborative groups (Meier, 2020), including opportunities for students to learn in a social context, with and from their peers (Donato & MacCormick, 1994), and solve tasks and problems together (Swain & Lapkin, 2000). Classroom approaches that reflect social and collaborative learning will influence the choice of classroom activities and experiences as well as the class layout.

Another influential theory that underpins the teaching of EAL/D is the communicative approach (Nunan, 1987; Swarbrick, 1993). In such an approach, a range of communicative activities are designed where students will have a need to use the target language to communicate with each other (Nunan, 1987) often using real or real-simulated tasks, with a particular purpose. Important to this approach is the belief that there should be a focus on meaning during communication and the task. In particular, focus should be on the meaning of the message in the target language before

the form or grammar of the language (Krashen & Terrell, 1983). This approach provides a need for learners to communicate and understand meaning (Krashen & Terrell, 1983). Pair work is often recommended for communicative tasks because pairs provide increased talk time for learners. When considering the content for communication, age-appropriate, cognitively appropriate content is important (Piaget, 1972) so that EAL/D learners are not just learning new English names for things already known in another language but are developing new content knowledge and skills in addition to their development of English (Bower et al., 2020).

Non-verbal communication is also important for EAL/D (Kaluska, 2013). It is recognised that non-verbal communication supports communication overall and can be used to assist meaning-making and comprehension for language learners. Non-verbal strategies that may support EAL/D include actions, gestures, body language, sound-effects, intonation, and voice volume. The use of images, video, and concrete items or realia provide context clues for meaning and tap into learners' prior knowledge and also offer effective ways to support EAL/D comprehension and communication. Maximising use of these non-verbal supports in the classroom can maximise students' comprehension of English. It is also important to consider strategies that build EAL/D learners' comprehension without requiring production. Since receptive language develops before productive language (Davies, 1976), strategies that build EAL/D learners' comprehension prior to them being required to produce English, and alongside their early English production, is very beneficial. To support this process, teachers need to provide lots of comprehensible input (Krashen, 1983), safe spaces for language rehearsal and risk taking, with an emphasis on building confidence and fluency.

In the past, there was often a deficit view of the limited English of EAL/D learners with focus placed on filling the gaps of their limited English abilities. Currently there is a much more widespread understanding that these learners come with language skills that are just not in English. The role of their other language/s and the importance of them for their learning is becoming more readily acknowledged. Translanguaging is a pedagogical approach with bilingual and multilingual learners that acknowledges and uses learners' full linguistic repertoires (Garcia, 2009). The home language/s of learners can be used in a variety of ways in classrooms as springboards for their learning and to make connections between their knowledge and understandings across languages. This is based on the belief that all the languages of learners are important for their learning (Busch, 2012) and are interconnected and integrated (Stroud & Heugh, 2011). This includes oral language, reading, and writing. Using home languages is important for EAL/D learners to be able to express their full knowledge in school, to communicate in their strongest language, to transfer knowledge in their home language to English, and to use their home language to discuss their developing English. It is not important for teachers to know or use the languages of the students because translanguaging is beneficial for the learners themselves.

A wide range of strategies and resources can help stimulate translanguaging in classrooms, including having class routine words and theme words displayed in English and the home languages of the students, and may also include pictures. Bilingual resources such as bilingual dictionaries, books, posters, listening material, internet resources, apps, and classroom environmental print, can all also support classroom translanguaging. Translanguaging presents EAL/D learners as language knowers, provides an L2 (+) learning environment for all students, shows a valuing of languages and provides an important way for learners to use their language knowledge, experiences and skills to support their further learning and are also valuable cognitive resources for learners. To

enact translanguaging pedagogies in classrooms, the translanguaging design principles identified by (Rowe, 2018) are important to consider; "... valuing students' languages and cultures, modelling translanguaging, providing authentic opportunities for multilingual communication, inviting two-way translation, composing dual-language texts, and connecting students with bilingual or multilingual audiences" (Rowe, 2018, p.31). To maximise multilingual students' learning, translanguaging is an important approach to incorporate with EAL/D teaching and learning.

The social and emotional needs of EAL/D learners also need to be considered and supported in order for language development to take place (Adams & Richie, 2017; Lau & Shea, 2024). EAL/D learners need to feel safe and secure in the classroom environment, with reduced levels of anxiety, and feel free to express themselves without fear of mistakes, correction or reprimand. Teachers need to understand the higher cognitive demands required of learners when functioning in a second/ additional language and provide options for them to have a break from English (such as through reading familiar books in their home language/s), and to provide stress release (such as through activities such as playdough, shredding paper, quiet reading/ browsing). The importance of other school subjects that may not have such a high English demand, such as sport, art, and music, are critical to providing balance in the day for EAL/D learners. Also of importance to supporting the social and emotional needs of EAL/D learners, are classroom strategies that support students to settle in, develop friendships, and provide peer support. Providing a fun, task-based (Long, 2014) learning environment or language learning with games (Wright et al., 2006) also helps to engage learners and support their social and emotional needs when learning.

It is recognised that effective EAL/D-inclusive teaching practices are effective teaching practices for all learners. Therefore, teachers are not being expected to create many separate lessons or teaching materials for the various needs of all the learners in their classes, but rather, adapt lessons and add strategies that can be more accessible and inclusive for all learners, including EAL/D learners. Therefore, considering differentiation strategies for EAL/D learners is important. These may include; differentiation by conditions, where extensive or reduced support is provided, differentiation by activity, where the steps required in an activity are reduced or increased and simple or more complex language is used, differentiation by expectations, where shorter, simplified responses with a high acceptance of errors, or longer, complex responses are expected, differentiation by text, where familiar repetitive texts with pictorial cues or unfamiliar extended texts are used (Victorian Curriculum and Assessment Authority, 2012). EAL/D learners also benefit from having a known routine and structure. Visual timetables and image-based instruction cards can be useful for this. A range of strategies to scaffold EAL/D learners' production of English are also very beneficial, such as providing a model, vocabulary lists, sentence starters, graphic organisers, images, and real objects. Reinforcement of language with multiple exposures (Department of Education and Training Victoria, 2023) and repetition are also important.

This overview of some key EAL/D theories and literature provide some key approaches and strategies to consider for teaching EAL/D learners. It is acknowledged that the unique school context and individual learner needs are critical when teachers adopt approaches and strategies, and that teachers and learners both benefit from a wide range of strategies to support teaching and learning. Therefore, teachers should be empowered to design learning experiences for their own learners in their own contexts informed by the wide range of theories and literature.

The Study

In the multicultural and multilingual context of Melbourne, Australia, it is particularly important for teachers to explore pedagogical practices that are inclusive to the diverse needs of EAL/D learners. The whole primary school staff of a large co-educational Independent (private) school in Melbourne engaged in a one-year long series of professional learning focussed on EAL/D with author 1, a university academic/teacher/researcher. One professional learning session was held at the beginning of the year, followed by one session each school term (5 sessions in total) dispersed with teachers conducting action research in their classrooms in response to their learnings and their EAL/D student needs within their own classroom contexts. The guiding question that drove the action research was *What are the EAL/D learning needs (of the class, or of a learner or learners) and how can they be met informed by an evidence base of research?* One of the teachers from the school, author 2, was particularly engaged in the process, had numerous innovative and effective examples of classroom practice to share that were the result of their action research, and expressed interest in collaborating to share their practice with others via this medium of a publication. Author 1 and 2 wrote this article together which became a wonderful example of sharing our knowledge and practices with each other and building on these with professional discussions. It is also hoped that by sharing these more widely, it may support other teachers, either as reminders of strategies or to introduce new strategies to them.

Method

Action research

Action research (Cohen et al., 2011) was used as a key strategy of embedding professional learning into practical classroom application. Action research involves an ongoing cycle of classroom action to implement a strategy and observe its impacts in the classroom after which modifications may be made based on those observations, then further cycles of action research are undertaken. Action research in this study involved implementing a new approach or strategy, observing the impact of it in the classroom, gathering observations and/ or feedback, reflecting on the effectiveness of the strategy and students' learning, modifying the approach or strategy based on the observations or outcomes, and then repeating the cycle. There may be many cycles of this practice. Action research provides agency and autonomy for teachers to explore aspects of professional learning in their own classrooms, with their own learners, and direct their own action resulting from professional learning.

The Timperley Evidence-Based Professional Learning Cycle (Timperley et al., 2007; Timperley, 2010) was considered within the action research process. This enables evaluation of the impact of professional learning on teachers' practice and on students' learning through its five dimensions: 1. What do my students need to be able to know and be able to do? 2. What do I need to know and be able to do in response to my students' needs? 3. How do I go about deepening my knowledge and refining my skills? 4. What happens in the classroom when I apply my learning? and 5. What impact did my learning have on my practice and on my students' learning?

In addition to the professional learning sessions including the sharing of research and strategies with the teachers, teachers' own ideas and experiences were generated through discussions and informed the classroom action research. Each teacher's action research differed according to

their needs, the needs of the learners in their classes, and were self-selected by teachers according to what they were interested in trialling in their own classrooms. There was an emphasis on the action research being needs-driven, informing real practice, and including classroom action. A starting point for teachers' consideration was their 'problems of practice' (Henriksen et al., 2017) which included such things as challenges, difficulties, and things that would make a difference if improved.

The examples of practice reported on in this article are one teacher's EAL/D strategies from their action research journey that were found to be effective in terms of enabled support to the EAL/D learner/s. Reflections on their experiences in their own practice are also shared.

Examples of Effective Classroom Practice

This section is divided into three key parts. In the first part, the context of the school and of the classroom is explained providing such information as year level, number of students, backgrounds, and learning needs. In the second part, the strategy is described, and the actions of the teacher and learner/s are explained. In the third part, there is a discussion of the implementation of the strategy, including anecdotal evidence, and an explanation of what the teacher noticed in the classroom, with a student, group or class. Overall, what worked, what was noticed, what practices will be continued, and what would be changed in the future, are then shared. The second and third parts are shared for each of the four examples of practice.

Context

The school is an Independent (private) school in Melbourne Australia. Each year level in the school has between 40% and 85% of its students with EAL/D. The dominant language other than English is Mandarin. There are also a very small number of speakers of Cantonese, Hindi, Punjabi and Korean at the school. The majority of classes at the school have more EAL/D students than non-EAL/D students.

The teacher-co-author who shares the examples of practice in this article is a Year 2 teacher at the school. The Year 2 class consists of 18 students. Fourteen speak Mandarin at home, and 13 of these students speak and understand English to varying degrees. One student was non-English speaking at the commencement of the school year. Two students have identified learning needs in literacy, requiring targeted support. The classroom environment emphasises inclusivity, with a focus on language acquisition and literacy development to support students across all subject areas, particularly those from multilingual backgrounds.

Data

Example of practice 1: Speaking and listening protocol; back-to-back/face-to-face

Strategy description. This strategy encourages structured speaking and listening. Students pair up and stand back-to-back, ensuring they respect personal space. The teacher asks a question, giving students time to think. Once they have an answer, they signal readiness by quietly showing a thumbs up on their chest. When all students are ready, the teacher will ask them to turn to face their partner. One student speaks first while the other listens attentively, maintaining eye contact.

The teacher roams listening to the conversations but not interrupting. After both have spoken, they return back-to-back and stand quietly, signalling they are finished. Once all pairs are again standing quietly back-to-back the teacher may invite pairs to share their partner's response, or students may be given the opportunity to rotate partners to gain new perspectives.

Discussion of strategy. In the back-to-back face-to-face protocol, significant improvements were noticed in both confidence and language use, especially among EAL/D students. This strategy was used with the whole class, pairing students with varying levels of English proficiency. The back-to-back portion allowed them to focus solely on listening to the teacher's question about a recently read text, without the pressure of having to respond immediately. This was particularly helpful for quieter students or those lacking confidence in their English.

When they transitioned to face-to-face, an immediate shift was observed. The conversations became more animated, with students using more facial expressions and gestures to aid their communication. A few students began naturally correcting each other's language use, which was encouraging, as it showed peer support and collaboration. The structured nature of the activity also ensured everyone had a chance to speak and listen, which balanced participation.

What worked particularly well was how the protocol scaffolded oral language practice in a supportive environment, making it adaptable across subjects. When the students were asked about the protocol, they mentioned that it gave them more time to think about their responses and ensured everyone had a chance to speak, unlike typical classroom discussions where only a few students participated. It also allowed the limited-English speaking student to practice their English and interact with classmates they hadn't engaged with before, giving them the confidence and reassurance that they were being understood by others when not engaging in their home language. Something to consider in the future for this protocol would be providing more language prompts for EAL/D students who may need additional support, ensuring they have the vocabulary and phrases needed to participate fully in the partner discussion.

Example of practice 2: Roll and read strategy

Strategy description. The Roll and Read activity is designed to enhance students' reading fluency, pronunciation, and sentence comprehension through a fun, game-based approach. It is particularly effective for EAL/D students, as the sentences are tailored to match class developmental levels. In the activity, students roll a die, match the number to a sentence on their sheet, and read it aloud. They work with a partner who listens and checks for accuracy. If the student reads the sentence correctly, they colour in the sentence. If not, they wait for their next turn to try again. This activity promotes oral reading and active listening in a relaxed, supportive environment, with a focus on practice, peer feedback, and gradual improvement in reading fluency.

Discussion of strategy. The Roll and Read activity worked effectively for EAL/D learners in the classroom. The randomness added by rolling the die kept students engaged and curious to see which sentence they would land on. What was noticed was that EAL/D students responded well to the game format, as it provided them with a structured yet fun way to practice their reading. The peer feedback aspect was particularly helpful; when paired with proficient speakers, EAL/D students were supported in both pronunciation and comprehension.

One notable success was the reduction in anxiety around reading aloud. Since the activity is presented as a game and allows for mistakes (with flexibility for incorrect pronunciation), EAL/D

students were more willing to take risks with new words or sounds. This led to increased participation and confidence in reading.

What worked especially well was the repetition and the opportunity to practice multiple times. Each time students landed on the same sentence, they had the chance to improve their accuracy and fluency, reinforcing learning through practice.

Next time, more vocabulary could be added to support learners before the game to ensure that EAL/D learners are familiar with the words they will encounter. Additionally, visual aids or sentence starters could be provided to further assist beginners who may struggle with sentence comprehension.

Example of practice 3: Comprehension strategy; Listen, match and colour

Strategy description. In this strategy, a non-English speaking student demonstrated their comprehension of a story by listening to questions in their home language on an iPad and responding by selecting and colouring the correct picture on a worksheet. The process begins with a review of the story to ensure familiarity with key events and characters. Then, using the iPad, the student listens to comprehension questions, which are translated into their home language. After hearing each question, the student identifies the appropriate picture from a set of images and colours it according to the instructions. This method helps assess comprehension without requiring proficiency in oral production or written English.

Discussion of strategy. The Listen, Match, and Colour strategy proved highly effective in engaging the EAL/D students, particularly those with limited or no English oral production proficiency. The students were able to follow the questions and instructions through audio prompts in their home language, which provided a sense of comfort and familiarity. This allowed the students to focus on the content and meaning of the story without the added pressure of decoding written English questions. By relying on pictures to answer, the students demonstrated a clear understanding of key story elements, such as how characters felt or what actions they took, by correctly colouring the dot on the corresponding images.

One of the most successful aspects of this strategy was the multimodal approach. The combination of listening, visual cues, and a simple action (colouring) created a manageable and engaging task for the students. The students were noticeably more willing to participate and appeared more confident, likely because they were able to engage in the lesson through their home language and work independently. This bridged the gap between their comprehension of the story and their ability to demonstrate that understanding.

Using pictures as answers helped reduce the cognitive load for the students, who might otherwise have struggled with reading in English. The colouring activity added a kinaesthetic component, enhancing the student's focus and engagement. This assessment method allowed the student to demonstrate their comprehension in a meaningful and low-stress way while participating in an activity that was similar to what the rest of the class was doing but adapted to suit their needs.

This strategy will be used with other non-English-speaking students in the future, as it creates a scaffolded learning environment where they can demonstrate comprehension without being limited by language barriers. As students advance in their English skills, the next step would be to introduce a combination of picture responses and simple questions written in English that require a written response. Incorporating peer support and allowing bilingual students to work together to reinforce their understanding will also be considered for future practice.

Example of practice 4: Sequencing activity

Strategy description. This strategy focusses on helping a non-English speaking EAL/D student understand the sequence of events in a mentor text through a combination of vocabulary introduction, bilingual reading, and hands-on sequencing activities. Key vocabulary is introduced using real objects, images, and gestures, ensuring the words are clarified in both the student's home language and English. The text is read first in the student's home language (either via a translation app or an EAL/D support person) and then in English, with pauses to check for understanding. The student engages in a sequencing activity, cutting out simple sentences with corresponding pictures from the story and arranging them in order with support. The activity concludes with a review to reinforce comprehension.

Discussion of strategy. When implementing this strategy, it was noticeable that using bilingual reading and visual supports significantly enhanced the student's engagement and understanding of the text. Introducing key vocabulary in both the student's home language and English was essential, as it provided a foundation for their comprehension. The use of real objects and gestures, along with the vocabulary, helped the student connect new words with familiar concepts. While reading the text, checking for understanding by encouraging the student to point to relevant images was effective in reinforcing the link between the text and the visuals.

The sequencing activity was designed as a whole-class task but differentiated to accommodate varying developmental levels. For this EAL/D student, it worked especially well because it provided a hands-on, interactive method to engage with the story while fostering a sense of inclusion by participating in the same activity as their peers. Cutting out the sentences, which were supported by pictures from the book, not only helped improve fine motor skills but also encouraged deeper processing of the story's events. As the student arranged the sentences in the correct sequence, their ability to recall the events grew stronger. Additionally, prompting the student to practice the newly learned vocabulary was a key success in reinforcing language retention.

The visual and kinaesthetic elements of the lesson were crucial for the student's understanding, providing easier access than language alone. The student's connection to, comprehension of, and enjoyment of the text became clear when they repeatedly requested to have it read throughout the week. Going forward, the approach will continue to be used but the pace will be slowed to allow more discussion during the bilingual reading phase, as the student benefitted from frequent pauses to process the information. Furthermore, the future exploration of additional digital translation tools to enhance the home language reading experience is planned, ensuring smoother transitions between languages without having to rely on other students for translation support in class.

Discussion

The collection of examples of practice shared is the result of evidence-informed cycles of action research carried out by one teacher in their classroom. The iterative process of in-context, in-classroom trialling of strategies, building on their own teaching techniques and refining what works in their classroom context, with their learners, and reflecting on their practice and their learners' learning, reflects the cycles of action research that teachers engage in. It is acknowledged that this article focuses on the exploratory classroom practice with reflections and considerations for future use without a description of the cyclical iterative action research process, and this is a limitation of this research. Iterative cycles were undertaken before reaching the examples of practice shared

and may still continue into the future, however, these are not reported on in this article. The action research process emphasises the importance of personalising professional learning for individual teachers, for their own classroom context, and their own learners, considering learners' unique needs, interests, and language levels. Despite a personalised approach, it is recognised that the learnings from action research can be beneficial to other teachers too.

The examples of practice shared in this article identified effective strategies for EAL/D learners, identified the benefits to students from the strategies, and also provided a range of considerations for the future use and adaptation of the strategies. Therefore, these three themes: 1. effective strategies for EAL/D learners, 2. benefits to EAL/D students from these strategies, and 3. considerations for the future use and adaptation of the strategies, were used to analyse the four examples of practice and the resulting data about each of the themes is shared in the form of lists to follow. Next to each point in the collection is a number in brackets that corresponds with the example of practice number. It is hoped that these may support teachers of EAL/D learners when making pedagogical decisions about their practice and support them in selecting strategies that help develop EAL/D learners' areas of need.

Effective strategies for EAL/D learners included those that:

Provided think time (1),
Included non-verbal communication (1),
Included peer support and collaboration to help EAL/D learners which also provided a source of modelling and guided corrections (1),
Included pair work for increased talk time (1, 2),
Included game-based learning (2),
Included fun repetition (2),
Were relaxed and supportive (2),
Were practice-focussed (2),
Included levelled options/ multi-needs/ differentiation (2, 3, 4),
Enabled comprehension without requiring English production (3),
Used home language to facilitate interaction with English content (3),
Provided comfort and familiarity when home language was integrated (3),
Used home language to help learners access English meaning and increase task participation (3),
Used pictures to identify meaning (3),
Included multimodal approaches (listening, visual cues, action/ colouring) (3),
Included iPad translation (3, 4),
Enabled words/ meaning to be clarified in home language (4),
Enabled bilingual reading (4),
Introduced key vocabulary before a task (including use of real objects, images, gestures) (4),
Used objects, gestures, vocabulary and images to connect new words with familiar concepts (4),
Were hands on, interactive, kinaesthetic (4),
Used visuals (4), and
Were inclusive tasks with options for all learners to do the same task in various ways at various levels (4).

Benefits to EAL/D students from these strategies included:

Increased English language use (1),
Increased confidence (1, 2, 3),
Increased curiosity (2),
Increased learners' willingness to take risks (2),
Reduced anxiety/ stress (2, 3),
Increased fun/ enjoyment (2, 4), and
Increased engagement and participation (2, 3, 4).

Considerations for the future use and adaptation of the strategies included:

Providing further prompts for EAL/D students such as vocabulary, and phrases (1),
Providing vocabulary support pre-game/pre-task (2),
Adding visual support (2),
Providing sentence starters (2),
Involving bilingual peers (3),
Slowing the pace (4),
Adding more discussion (4),
Adding more pauses and time to process (4), and
Further exploring digital translation tools (4).

This collection of points identifies the wide range of effective strategies that support EAL/D learners from the four examples of practice that were shared, and the benefits to EAL/D students from these strategies. This collection could be used by teachers to help select strategies for their teaching that address their EAL/D learners' needs. The collection also includes a range of considerations for the future use and adaptation of the strategies which could be applied to a wide range of strategies beyond the four examples of practice shared. These offer suggestions for the further modification of strategies that could enable greater support or provide further differentiation. It is hoped that teachers of EAL/D can benefit from the examples of practice shared and are encouraged to share their practice with others too.

Conclusion

In this article, we reported on four examples of effective EAL/D classroom practice that derived from one teacher's action research in their primary school classroom in Melbourne Australia. Their practice was grounded by their own cycles of action research and reflective practice relating to what worked in their classroom and in particular in addressing the needs of the learners. A series of EAL/D-specific professional learning undertaken by the whole school, including the co-author-teacher, provided a literature and theoretical basis for their exploration in addition to sample strategies provided in the series of professional learning. It is recognised that each teaching and learning context is different and that individual students all have unique needs, however, it is hoped that the examples of practice shared in this article may provide stimulus for other teachers working with students who have English as an additional language or dialect. This article also highlights the benefits of action research-focussed professional learning for teachers where new learnings can be directly trialled in teachers' own classrooms and reflected upon followed by further cycles of

iterative, responsive professional learning and further cycles of classroom-based action research. The emphasis of this article was on the exploratory classroom-based research which highlights the benefits for professional learning experience and knowledge and practice growth. Reporting research on the iterative cycles would have enriched this study and will be a consideration for future research. It is hoped that this process of combining professional learning with cycles of in-classroom action research for the authentic implementation of learning to practice, is a beneficial model for teachers, where they can explore their learnings and new ideas in their own classroom contexts and with their own learners, with the ultimate aim to improve EAL/D teaching and learning.

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